

Bibliographic Record

Article by G. P. Grabovoi published in "Электронная техника. Серия 3: Микроэлектроника" (1999)

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Deposit Information

Title of Zenodo deposit	Bibliographic record of an article by G. P. Grabovoi published in "Электронная техника. Серия 3: Микроэлектроника" (1999)
Creator of this record	Antonio Iadicicco
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The full text of the original article is not deposited in this Zenodo record. The purpose of the record is to provide an orderly bibliographic reference, a persistent Zenodo record, and a link to an external scan available online.

Article Described

Author	Г. П. Грабовой / Grigori P. Grabovoi
Original Russian title	Исследования и анализ фундаментальных определений оптических систем в предотвращении катастроф и прогнозно-ориентированном управлении микропроцессами
English rendering of the title	Research and analysis of fundamental definitions of optical systems in prevention of catastrophes and forecast-oriented control of microprocesses
Publication	Электронная техника. Серия 3: Микроэлектроника
Issue	выпуск 1(153)
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Bibliographic Reference

Грабовой Г. П. Исследования и анализ фундаментальных определений оптических систем в предотвращении катастроф и прогнозно-ориентированном управлении микропроцессами. Электронная техника. Серия 3: Микроэлектроника, выпуск 1(153), 1999, Москва, Центральный научно-исследовательский институт «Электроника».

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Prepared by

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